

(31.0%). In such situations, their actions were especially cruel. Criminal actions were preceded by the use of alcoholic beverages or drugs, which facilitated the onset of aggression. They often committed planned crimes in a group of people, acting as a leader.

Conclusion. Thus, aggressive illegal behavior is characteristic of persons, mainly with emotionally unstable, hysterical and mixed personality disorders (excitable, hypersthenic types). Aggression as a personality trait is formed in childhood and adolescence against the background of adverse factors (mainly microsocial and psychological) and exacerbates the dynamics of personality disorder. Clinical-dynamic and socio-psychological analysis revealed factors that determine the aggressive criminal behavior of subjects with personality disorders: improper upbringing and unfavorable psychotraumatic environment in a family with child abuse; substance abuse; repeated criminal acts in history; acute and chronic traumatic situations preceding the aggressive delict, negative dynamic shifts.

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METHOD OF DIRECT PROSTHETICS IN PATIENTS WITH GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS

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ABSTRACT

Indices of hygiene, gingival bleeding and RMA are significantly better in patients with proposed direct prosthetics in the long term after prosthetics compared with the period before treatment and in the group of patients in whom direct prosthetics were not used. Conclusions. the design of a direct fixed aesthetic prosthesis has advantages over other methods of orthopedic treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis of the II degree of development.

Keywords: generalized periodontitis, direct prosthetics, bone tissue atrophy, hygiene indices, bleeding gums.

Purpose: to increase the effectiveness of complex treatment of patients with partial loss of teeth and generalized periodontitis by using the proposed method of direct prosthetics.

The main problem of dentistry is the search for new methods for the prevention and treatment of periodontal tissue diseases. According to WHO, periodontal disease is the leading dental disease. Damage to periodontal tissues is accompanied by complex and profound disorders of biochemical, immunological, endocrine metabolic processes [1, 2]. This, in turn, leads to neurovascular disorders in periodontal tissues, causing changes in bone metabolism and metabolic processes of the entire periodontal tissue complex, the development of pathological tooth mobility and their loss. At the same time, the function of chewing is disturbed, areas of traumatic occlusion are created, and defects in the dentition occur [3,4]. Such a clinic requires complex treatment of patients, which includes therapeutic, surgical and orthopedic methods of treatment, pressure on the entire tissue complex affected by the pathological process. Removal of increased deformity to go to the preserved periodontal tissues in the process of chewing is a therapeutic factor and it can be done only with the help of orthopedic methods [5]. Of particular importance are orthopedic methods of treatment in case of partial absence of teeth, combined with generalized periodontitis, which makes it possible to prevent overload of preserved teeth. Significant importance in the treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis, complicated by partial loss of teeth, acquires direct prosthetics. Waiting tactics after the extraction of several teeth leads to an additional overload of the preserved teeth, which in turn causes an exacerbation of inflammatory processes, an increase in the pathological mobility of the teeth, and leads to their removal [6, 7, 8]. Therefore, in generalized periodontitis, the method of direct prosthetics with structures is important, the use of which will prevent the development of complications of the course of generalized periodontitis with partial loss of teeth, the process of atrophy of the bone tissue of the alveolar process after the removal of several teeth due to complications of generalized periodontitis.

We examined 108 people over 45 years old with II-III degree HP, in which the course of the disease was accompanied by partial loss of teeth. Depending on the method of orthopedic treatment, the patients were divided into groups: Group I - 31 patients who, immediately after tooth extraction, had a direct plastic partial lamellar removable im-diat-prosthesis placed on the preserved dentition along with their selective grinding; Group II - 39 patients who underwent conventional permanent prosthetics with fixed bridges 6 weeks after the removal of mobile teeth and wound healing; Group III - 38 patients who, after the removal of mobile teeth, were given a direct fixed, collapsible bridge prosthesis. Along with selective grinding, permanent prosthetics were carried out after 6 months. The control group consisted of 26 people with intact dentition. Studies of the state of the periodontium were carried out using the periodontal index, hygiene indices (IG-DI-S), (IG-SI-S), PMA, gum bleeding, the degree of tooth mobility and

the X-ray recession index, the combined periodontal index KPI were determined. The structural and functional state of the bone tissue was determined by the level of markers of bone tissue metabolism, the mineral density of the bone tissue of the alveolar process in the area of the interdental septa of the preserved teeth was determined using computed tomography. Studies of periodontal tissues were carried out before the removal of mobile and 6 weeks later, as well as 6 months and a year after permanent prosthetics.

Research results

A detailed analysis of the indexes of hygiene, bleeding of the gums, the state of periodontal inflammation in patients of three groups was carried out. 6 weeks after removal, they slightly improved in group I, the worst indicator was in group II and in group III of patients.

6 months after prosthetics, the indicators in groups I and II were at the level of 1.82 ± 0.05 and 1.81 ± 0.04 points, and in group III the hygiene index was 1.42 ± 0.02 points. A year after prosthetics, IG-DI-S was 2.03 ± 0.06 points in group I patients, the worst indicator was in patients of group II who did not have direct prosthetics - 2.23 ± 0.05 points, and this indicator was the best in patients of group III, who used a direct non-removable aesthetic prosthesis - 1.53 ± 0.05 points.

6 months after prosthetics, the indicators in groups I and II were at the level of 1.03 ± 0.13 and 1.08 ± 0.14 points, and in group III the hygiene index was 0.74 ± 0.15 points. A year after the orthopedic treatment, IG-SI-S in group I was

patients 1.29 ± 0.17 points, in patients of group II, who did not use direct prosthetics, it was

1.19 ± 0.16 points, and the best indicator was in patients of group III, who used a direct non-removable aesthetic prosthesis - 0.79 ± 0.16 points. Therefore, when analyzing the studied indicators of the periodontal condition in patients of three groups, we established significantly better indicators when using the design of a fixed aesthetic direct prosthesis, stabilization of the pathological process in periodontal tissues in the near and long term, improved oral hygiene and no progression of atrophy.

Conclusions

On the basis of clinical indicators, we found that the use of a direct non-removable aesthetic prosthesis design has advantages over other methods of orthopedic treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis of the 2nd degree of development. Indices of hygiene, bleeding gums and RMA are significantly preferable in patients with proposed direct prosthetics in the long term after prosthetics compared with the period before treatment and in the group of patients who did not receive direct prosthetic

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CLINICAL METHOD FOR THE RESTORATION OF DAMAGED NON-REMOVABLE METAL-PLASTIC PROSTHETIC SPLINTS

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the options for non-removable splinting using orthopedic structures for periodontal disease. The characteristics of tires, their advantages and disadvantages are given. The problems of periodontology in terms of overloading the abutment teeth with orthopedic structures and the moments of solving this with the help of orthopedic metal-plastic splints and removable dentures are outlined, and the clinical methodology for repairing (restoration) of damaged metal-plastic splints-prostheses is described in detail.

Keywords: periodontitis, tires, metal-plastic construction.

The use of splinting at the first signs of pathological tooth mobility is an integral component of the orthopedic treatment of this pathology [1]. All these are mainly manifestations of localized or generalized periodontitis [2], one of the serious diseases of the dentition. For fixed splinting, both stamped crowns and solid structures are used [5]. There are splinting structures using Polyglas tape [3, 4]. Stamped structures carry with them the absence of a cosmetic component, which is currently unacceptable. Purely cast crowns require hard tooth preparation and are very heavy, which does not contribute to effective complex orthopedic treatment of periodontitis. Metal-ceramic and metal-plastic-mass splinting structures have proven themselves better. They are much lighter than non-combined one-piece cast structures. Constructions made of cermet have proven themselves aesthetically well. But, taking into account the properties of cermets, with an antagonizing moment, "hard hits" are obtained. This does not help to alleviate the "provoked" periodontium. A metal-plastic construction is one of the few successful designs for aesthetic periodontal treatment by splinting. These structures are not heavy, and although the plastic has the ability to absorb oral fluid over time, they have a

softer contact antagonizing threshold, which is beneficial for the periodontium in the stabilization stage. Very often, with a fixed bite height in the frontal area and the absence of antagonistic teeth in lateral with orthognathic bite, the frame of the metal-plastic prosthesis on the lower jaw is exposed. This is due to the fact that patients refuse to use a removable prosthesis, and implantation in this case is not indicated or is too financially burdensome for the patient.

At the same time, the provoked periodontium receives an additional load, holding the full power of the dentoalveolar system. Usually, in this case, it is recommended to remove the metal-plastic prosthesis and make a new one, followed by unloading the dentition and manufacturing a removable structure. Removing the prosthesis is a laborious procedure, and re-manufacturing is expensive for the patient and does not spare the load on the periodontium. We offer a method for clinical restoration of the structure without it cutting (removal). We recommend doing this as follows. With the help of the silicone mass, we obtain an impression for the working model, and with the help of the alginate mass, for the auxiliary one. After that, the resulting models are plastered in an occluder, and the height of